

OPTIMAL PLACEMENT OF RECLOSERS AND SECTIONALIZERS IN A POWER DISTRIBUTION SYSTEM USING BAT ALGORITHM

Dr.M.Nalini Devi
Assistant Professor, Dept. of EEE
Mahatma Gandhi Institute of Technology
Hyderabad, India

Mrs S.Sudharani
Assistant Professor, Dept. of EEE
Mahatma Gandhi Institute of Technology
Hyderabad, India

Polavarapu Xavier Sanjeevi
Student, Dept. of EEE
Mahatma Gandhi Institute of Technology
Hyderabad, India

Doma Shruthi
Student, Dept. of EEE
Mahatma Gandhi Institute of Technology
Hyderabad, India

Bheemi Reddy Srinivas Reddy
Student, Dept. of EEE
Mahatma Gandhi Institute of Technology
Hyderabad, India

Abstract- In power distribution systems, sectionalizers and reclosers are installed to help with fault management. They work in tandem with circuit breakers. To achieve the highest level of system reliability, these should be installed in power distribution systems in the best possible way. In order to achieve this, an optimization problem is modeled in order to find the best location for the devices while simultaneously cutting down on the search space and computation time. Finding the best place for sectionalizers and reclosers in power distribution systems is the formulation of the optimization problem. In order to determine the most profitable installation strategy, the objective function is composed of reliability indices, equipment cost, and power loss incurred. Weighted sum approach has been used to combine all the parameters into a single multi objective function. This objective function is used as the fitness function in the optimization algorithm (bat algorithm) to achieve the best solution. Python console has been used to model a sample distribution system. Bat algorithm has been used to optimize the placement of these devices and the results have been plotted accordingly. The Bat Algorithm as it has a meta heuristic characteristic is not biased and hence is a good fit for deciding the optimal locations of reclosers and sectionalizers in a power distribution system.

Keywords- Power Distribution System, Sectionalizers, Reclosers, BAT algorithm and Python Console

I. INTRODUCTION

The last phase of electricity delivery is electric power distribution. From the transmission system, electricity is delivered to individual customers. Distribution substations use transformers to reduce the transmission voltage to a medium voltage between 2 kV and 33 kV after connecting to the transmission system. This medium voltage power is delivered to distribution transformers close to the customer's location via primary distribution lines. Once more, distribution transformers reduce the voltage to the level required for home appliances, industrial machinery, and lighting. Secondary distribution lines are frequently used to supply multiple customers from a single transformer. Service drops are used to attach each business and home clients to the secondary distribution lines. Customers demanding a much larger amount of power may be connected directly to the primary distribution level or the sub transmission level.

A power substation, which has switches and circuit breakers to allow the substation to be disconnected from the transmission grid or for distribution lines to be disconnected, is where the transmission to distribution transition takes place. Transformers reduce transmission voltages to primary distribution voltages, which are 11 kV. These circuits have a medium voltage, typically between 430 and 11,000 V. Power is sent from the transformer to the busbar, which has the ability to cut the distribution power off in several ways. Distribution lines receive power from the bus and then distribute it to customers. A sample power distribution system is shown in Fig 1.

Fig 1: Initial System Configuration

Z. Li et al. [1] focused on optimization model-based reliability assessment for distribution networks considering detailed placement of circuit breakers and switches due to their inherent simplicity, ease of control, and exceptional performance. M. Izadi et al. [2] worked on a MIP model for risk constrained switch placement in distribution networks. S. F. Santos et al [3] proposed analysis of switch automation based on active reconfiguration considering reliability, energy storage systems, and variable renewable.

M. Moradijoz et al [4] addressed Flexibility enhancement in active distribution networks through a risk-based optimal placement of sectionalizing switches. H. Karim et al [5] developed Switches optimal placement of automated distribution networks with probability customer interruption cost model. M. Safari [6] proposed a hybrid method for recloser and sectionalizer placement in distribution networks considering protection coordination, fault type and equipment malfunction. D. Lin et al [7] found optimal placement of multiple feeder terminal units using intelligent algorithms. A. Alam et al [8] developed switch and recloser placement in distribution system considering uncertainties in loads, failure rates, and repair rates. Mehrdad Ebrahimi et al [9] focused on learning-assisted model for optimal placement of protective devices and switches in power distribution systems.

II. MATHEMATICAL MODELLING

The Bat Algorithm (BA) is a metaheuristic optimization algorithm inspired by the echolocation behavior of bats. Introduced by Xin-She Yang in 2010, BA imitates the way bats use sound waves and echoes to locate prey and navigate their environment. The algorithm incorporates two key characteristics of bats' echolocation:

Loudness (A): How loudly a bat emits sound, which reduces as the bat gets closer to its prey (solution).

Pulse Emission Rate (r): The frequency at which a bat sends out pulses, which increases as the bat zeroes in on the prey (solution).

1) MATHEMATICAL FORMULATION

x_i be the position of bat i

v_i be the velocity of bat i

f_i be the frequency of bat i

A_i be the loudness of bat i

r_i be the pulse emission rate of bat i

2) FREQUENCY UPDATE:

Controls the velocity of bats and helps balance exploration (global search) and exploitation (local search). Typically varies between a minimum and maximum frequency

$$f_i = f_{min} + (f_{max} - f_{min}) \cdot \beta$$

β is a random variable in [0,1]

3) *VELOCITY UPDATE*

The speed of each bat, which determines the position updates in the search space.

$$v_i^{(t+1)} = v_i^t + (x_i^t - x_{best}) \cdot f_i$$

4) *POSITION UPDATE*

Represents the current solution of a bat in the search space.

$$x_i^{(t+1)} = x_i^t + v_i^{(t+1)}$$

5) *LOUDNESS UPDATE*

Simulates the loudness of the sound emitted by the bats. It decreases as the bats converge to a solution.

$$A_i^{(t+1)} = \alpha \cdot A_i^t$$

6) *PULSE RATE UPDATE*

Probability of emitting a pulse. It starts with a small value and increases as the algorithm progresses, encouraging local search.

$$r_i^{(t+1)} = r_i^t \cdot [1 - e^{-\gamma \cdot t}]$$

Along with these parameters there is one more important parameter “local search” which encourages the bats to search the local search space and update the local and global best solutions if found.

7) *LOCAL SEARCH*

$$x_{new} = x_{best} + \epsilon \cdot A_i^t$$

Given below is a table pertaining to the values of constants used in the Bat Algorithm and their purposes

TABLE I
Constants used in Bat Algorithm

Constant	Symbol	Purpose	Typical Values
Frequency Range	f_{min}, f_{max}	Controls step size	$f_{min} = 0$ $f_{max} = 2$
Initial Loudness	A_0	Intensity of exploration	$A_0 \in [0.5, 1.0]$
Pulse Emission Rate	r_0	Probability of local search	$r_0 \in [0.1, 0.5]$
Loudness Decay Factor	α	Governs loudness reduction	$\alpha \in [0.9, 1.0]$
Pulse Growth Factor	γ	Governs pulse rate increase	$\gamma \in [0.5, 1.0]$
Randomness	β	Ensures stochasticity	$0 \leq \beta \leq 1$
No of Iterations	T_{max}	Total no of iterations required	Depends on the problem and user interest

A. PROCEDURE OF BAT ALGORITHM:

1) Initialization

Define the parameters $n, f_{min}, f_{max}, r, A, T_{max}$

Initialize the position x_i and velocity of v_i each bat randomly.

Evaluate the objective function for each bat and identify the current best solution x_{best}

2) Frequency and Velocity Update

For each bat

$$f_i = f_{min} + (f_{max} - f_{min}) \cdot \beta$$

$$v_i^{(t+1)} = v_i^t + (x_i^t - x_{best}) \cdot f_i$$

3) Position Update

Update the position of the bat for each bat

$$x_i^{(t+1)} = x_i^t + v_i^{(t+1)}$$

4) Local Search (Exploitation)

If a random number $\text{rand}()$ is greater than r_i perform local search near the current best solution:

$$x_{new} = x_{best} + \epsilon \cdot A_i^t$$

Where ϵ is a random number in $[-1, 1]$

5) Pulse emission and loudness update:

Accept the new solution if:

A random number is less than A_i , and

The objective function value of the new position is better than the previous one.

Update the pulse rate r_i and loudness A_i

$$A_i^{(t+1)} = \alpha \cdot A_i^t$$

$$r_i^{(t+1)} = r_i^t \cdot [1 - e^{-\gamma \cdot t}]$$

6) Update best solution

Update x_{best} if a better solution is found

Repeat the above steps until the max no of iterations is reached or the convergence criteria is satisfied

B. Formulation Of The Objective Function

For our problem of optimal placement of reclosers and sectionalizers in a power distribution system we are considering a multi objective – objective function. The following parameters are involved in the formulation of the objective function: SAIDI, SAIFI, Power Loss, Cost.

1) Final Objective Function

All the above parameters are merged into a single objective function using weighted sum approach and the final objective function is obtained as follows:

$$\text{MINIMIZE: } F(x) = w_1 \cdot \text{SAIDI}(x) + w_2 \cdot \text{SAIFI}(x) + w_3 \cdot \text{POWER LOSS}(x) + w_4 \cdot \text{TOTAL COST}(x)$$

w_1, w_2, w_3, w_4 are weights of the parameters SAIDI, SAIFI, Power Loss, Total Cost respectively

The above combined function is used as the fitness function in the bat algorithm. The algorithm is used to evaluate the possible solutions and find out the best solution among those from the search space.

III.CODE ANALYSIS

A. System Modeling

The code simulates a simplified distribution network with a substation, feeders, and load points. Key components modeled include:

- 1) **Potential Device Locations:** Six specific points are defined where either a recloser or a sectionalizer *could* be installed, each with an associated cost.
- 2) **Load Data:** Four distinct loads are specified, each with active power (P), reactive power (Q), and crucially, a number of connected customers. This customer count is essential for calculating reliability indices (SAIDI and SAIFI).
- 3) **Network Structure (Implicit):** While a graphical network structure like networkx is *not* explicitly built in this version, the code implicitly represents connectivity through the relationship between loads and their upstream "section indices" (representing the location of the protective device immediately preceding the load).

B. Optimization Objective Function

The core of the optimization is the objective function, which the algorithm aims to minimize. It is a multi-objective function combining four key factors:

- 1) **SAIDI (System Average Interruption Duration Index):** A measure of the total duration of customer interruptions.
- 2) **SAIFI (System Average Interruption Frequency Index):** A measure of the total number of customer interruptions.
- 3) **Power Loss:** Represents energy inefficiency in the network.
- 4) **Total Installation Cost:** The sum of costs for all placed devices.

These four objectives are combined into a single fitness value using predefined weights (0.35 for SAIDI, 0.35 for SAIFI, 0.20 for Power Loss, 0.10 for Cost). The algorithm seeks a device placement that achieves the best possible balance according to these priorities.

Crucially, it is noted that the functions `calculate_power_loss` and `calculate_reliability_indices` in the provided code are explicitly stated as placeholders. They implement simplified logic (e.g., based on the number of devices placed or random factors) rather than performing detailed power system simulations (like load flow or fault analysis based on network topology, impedances, and failure rates). For a real-world application, these placeholder functions must be replaced with accurate power system analysis modules.

C. Optimization Algorithm: Bat Algorithm

Fig 2 represents a detailed procedure of the implementation of Bat Algorithm. This flow chat is further used to build the python code for the bat algorithm..

The Bat Algorithm is employed as the search mechanism to find the optimal device placement. It is a metaheuristic inspired by the echolocation behavior of bats. In this implementation:

Fig 2: Flow Chart of Bat Algorithm

- 1) Each "bat" represents a candidate solution, which is a binary vector of length 6 (corresponding to the 6 potential locations). A '1' at an index means a device is placed at that location, and '0' means no device.
- 2) The algorithm iteratively updates the "position" (device placement) and "velocity" of each bat based on:
 - 3) Their frequency (related to their movement speed).
 - 4) Their distance to the current best solution found globally.
 - 5) A mechanism for local search (random walk) and loudness/pulse rate to balance exploration (searching new areas) and exploitation (refining promising areas).
 - 6) A sigmoid function is used to convert the continuous "velocity" updates into probabilities for making binary decisions (placing a 1 or 0) at each location.
- 7) The algorithm continues for a set number of iterations (150), tracking the best fitness value found over time.

D. Results and Output

The code's execution provides the following outputs:

- 1) Confirmation of system parameters and load data.
- 2) An iteration log showing the convergence of the "Best Fitness" value, demonstrating how the algorithm improves the solution quality over time until it stabilizes.
- 3) The final "Best Placement Configuration" as a binary vector.
- 4) A "Device Placement Plan" translating the binary vector into a clear list indicating which specific device (recloser/sectionalizer) is placed at each named location and the total cost of this placement.
- 5) The calculated values of the individual objectives (Estimated Power Loss, SAIDI, SAIFI, Total Cost) for the final optimal placement found, using the placeholder calculation functions.
- 6) A convergence plot visualizing the improvement in the best fitness value across iterations.

IV. RESULTS

A. Code Output

Starting BAT Algorithm for Optimal Placement...

System Voltages (Informational): Primary=11.0kV, Secondary=0.433kV

Number of potential locations: 6

Population size: 40, Max Iterations: 150

Weights: SAIDI=0.35, SAIFI=0.35, Loss=0.20, Cost=0.10

Load Configuration:

Load1: Type=industrial, P=500 kW, Q=242 kVAR, Customers=10 (End of Sec 1)

Load2: Type=residential, P=300 kW, Q=99 kVAR, Customers=200 (End of Sec 2)

Load3: Type=industrial, P=450 kW, Q=218 kVAR, Customers=5 (End of Sec 4)

Load4: Type=residential, P=350 kW, Q=115 kVAR, Customers=250 (End of Sec 5)

Total Customers: 465

Iteration 0: Best Fitness = 0.321229

Iteration 10: Best Fitness = 0.295906

Iteration 20: Best Fitness = 0.295906

Iteration 30: Best Fitness = 0.295877

Iteration 40: Best Fitness = 0.295877

Iteration 50: Best Fitness = 0.295877

Iteration 60: Best Fitness = 0.295877

Iteration 70: Best Fitness = 0.295877

Iteration 80: Best Fitness = 0.295877

Iteration 90: Best Fitness = 0.295877

Iteration 100: Best Fitness = 0.295877

Iteration 110: Best Fitness = 0.295877

Iteration 120: Best Fitness = 0.295877

Iteration 130: Best Fitness = 0.295877

Iteration 140: Best Fitness = 0.295877

Iteration 150: Best Fitness = 0.295877

Optimization Finished!

Best Combined Objective Function Value: 0.295877

Best Placement Configuration (0=No Device, 1=Device): [1 1 1 1 0 1]

Device Placement Plan:

Location 0 (R1): Place recloser (Cost: 15000)

Location 1 (S1): Place sectionalizer (Cost: 5000)

Location 2 (S2): Place sectionalizer (Cost: 5000)

Location 3 (R2): Place recloser (Cost: 15000)

Location 4 (S3): No Device

Location 5 (S4): Place sectionalizer (Cost: 5000)

Objective Values for Best Placement (using placeholder functions):

Estimated Power Loss: 49.93 kW

Estimated SAIDI: 0.6393 hrs/cust/yr

Estimated SAIFI: 0.3836 int/cust/yr

Total Cost: 45000.00

Fig 3: Optimized System Configuration

Fig 3 represents the optimal placement of reclosers and sectionalizers in the considered sample distribution system (fig 1) based on the results obtained from the python code execution.

V. CONCLUSION

Bat Algorithm has been successfully applied in Python to determine the optimal placement of reclosers and sectionalizers within a power distribution system. The objective was to minimize a combined function considering reliability (SAIDI, SAIFI), power loss, and installation cost across 6 potential locations. The optimization identified a best placement configuration involving 5 devices: 2 reclosers and 3 sectionalizers. This configuration resulted in a total estimated installation cost of 45,000 INR. The estimated performance metrics for this optimized setup were a SAIDI of 0.6393 hrs/cust/yr, a SAIFI of 0.3836 int/cust/yr, and an estimated power loss of 49.93 kW. The Bat Algorithm effectively converged to a solution with a best fitness value of 0.295877, demonstrating its capability to navigate the multi-objective search space. The results underscore the potential of intelligent optimization techniques to identify cost-effective device placements that contribute to improved system reliability and operational efficiency in power distribution networks.

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